

Impaired prepulse inhibition in APP/PS1 mice is accompanied by substantial morphological changes in neurons of the central auditory system and hippocampus

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ABSTRACT

Auditory dysfunction is increasingly recognized as a non-cognitive feature of Alzheimer's disease (AD). We examined auditory processing and neuronal morphology in APP^{swe}/PSEN1^{dE9} (APP/PS1) transgenic mice, a model of AD. Ten-month-old male APP/PS1 and wild-type (WT) littermates were tested for auditory thresholds using auditory brainstem responses (ABR) and for sensorimotor gating using prepulse inhibition (PPI) of the acoustic startle reflex.

ABR thresholds did not differ between groups across tested frequencies (2–16 kHz), indicating preserved peripheral hearing. In contrast, APP/PS1 mice showed significantly impaired PPI at 4, 12, and 20 kHz prepulses and displayed exaggerated startle responses to high-intensity stimuli. Exploratory and anxiety-like behavior, assessed in the open field and elevated plus maze, did not differ between groups. Morphological analysis of Golgi–Cox-stained neurons revealed widespread dendritic pathology in the inferior colliculus, medial geniculate body and auditory cortex, as well as in hippocampal CA1. Compared with WT, APP/PS1 neurons exhibited shorter dendrites, reduced branching, and lower spine density, accompanied by markedly decreased dendritic complexity in Sholl analyses.

These findings demonstrate that sensorimotor gating deficits in APP/PS1 mice are accompanied by degeneration in central auditory and hippocampal circuits; however, a contribution of peripheral degeneration cannot be excluded. The data highlights the vulnerability of auditory midbrain and thalamic structures in this model of AD and suggests that dendritic alterations along the auditory pathway may contribute to central auditory dysfunction and serve as potential early biomarkers of disease.

1. Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is characterized not only by progressive cognitive decline but also by a range of non-cognitive symptoms, including auditory dysfunction. The APP^{swe}/PSEN1^{dE9} (APP/PS1) mouse line is a widely used model that develops amyloid deposition at 4–6 months of age, accompanied by neuronal and dendritic alterations (Jankowsky et al., 2001) and spinal motor neurons (Garcia-Alloza et al., 2006). In these mice, reduced amplitudes of auditory cortex (AC) evoked

responses have been reported, together with early accumulation of amyloid precursor protein (APP) in the AC as early as 2 months of age (Mei et al., 2021). However, reports on auditory thresholds in APP/PS1 mice are inconsistent: some studies describe progressive hearing loss (Liu et al., 2020), whereas others found no significant impairment (Na et al., 2023).

Prepulse inhibition (PPI) of the acoustic startle response is a sensitive measure of auditory system integrity and sensorimotor coordination. The startle reaction is mediated by a neural circuit involving the

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auditory nerve, cochlear root neurons, the caudal pontine reticular formation, and spinal motor neurons, and represents a motor response of the body to a sudden, intense acoustic stimulus. This startle reaction can be modulated by sensory stimulation that precedes the startle-eliciting stimulus. When the preceding (prepulse) stimulus is auditory, the inferior colliculus also participates in the modulation of the response (for review, see Lauer et al., 2017; Gómez-Nieto et al., 2020). A reduction in PPI reflects impaired sensorimotor gating, which normally suppresses excessive behavioral responses to salient stimuli. The hippocampus and entorhinal cortex are critically involved in regulating PPI, as well. Wang et al. (2012) reported reduced PPI in 7- and 22-month-old APP/PS1 mice compared with age-matched controls, while startle responses to pulse-alone stimuli were comparable between groups. In contrast, Ewers et al. (2006) found reduced PPI only in APP/PS1 mice with a high amyloid burden in the cortex. These discrepancies motivated us to investigate whether PPI of the startle response is consistently altered in APP/PS1 mice compared with controls.

Morphological analyses of APP/PS1 mice have demonstrated the presence of senile plaques and cerebral amyloid angiopathy (Garcia-Alloza et al., 2006). Subsequent studies described swollen dystrophic neurites, loss of dendritic spines, and reduced dendritic area in these animals (Moolman et al., 2004). Three-dimensional analyses of dentate gyrus spines further revealed a marked decrease in the frequency of large spines, even in plaque-free regions (Knafo et al., 2009). Despite these observations, no systematic study has examined dendritic morphology in APP/PS1 mice, particularly within central auditory structures. Given the functional changes reported in the auditory system of this model, we hypothesized that structural alterations may also be present in the inferior colliculus (IC), medial geniculate body (MGB), and auditory cortex (AC), as well as in the hippocampus. Consistent with this hypothesis, we found pronounced reductions in dendritic arborization across these regions, in parallel with impaired sensorimotor integration reflected in reduced PPI. In addition, exploratory and anxiety-like behaviors were assessed in the open field and elevated plus maze as complementary non-auditory tasks.

2. Methods

2.1. Animals

APP_{swe}/PSEN1_{dE9} (APP/PS1) transgenic mice were maintained as hemizygotes and crossed with C57BL/6 *J* × C3H wild-type mice to generate experimental animals. APP/PS1 offspring carried one copy each of the human APP_{swe} and PSEN1_{dE9} transgenes, whereas wild-type littermates lacked both transgenes and served as controls. Genotyping was performed to identify carriers of both mutant alleles (APP_{swe} and PSEN1_{dE9}), referred to as APP/PS1 mice, and non-carriers, referred to as wild-type (WT) littermates. Only male mice aged 10 months were used in this study. For behavioral testing, 10 WT and 9 APP/PS1 mice were included; one APP/PS1 animal was excluded from elevated plus maze analysis due to technical issues. For auditory brainstem response (ABR) recordings, 9 WT and 9 APP/PS1 mice were tested, as one WT animal was not evaluated. For morphological analyses, brains from 10 WT and 9 APP/PS1 mice were processed, except for the inferior colliculus, where usable data were obtained from 9 WT and 9 APP/PS1 animals due to tissue damage in one WT brain. Animals were housed in groups of 2–5 in an accredited facility at the Institute of Physiology of the Czech Academy of Sciences, under controlled temperature and humidity, with a 12/12 h light/dark cycle (lights on at 6:00 AM). All experiments were approved by the local Animal Care Committee (Project No. 51–2022-P) and conducted in accordance with the Animal Protection Code of the Czech Republic and EU Directive 2010/63/EU.

2.2. The open field and elevated plus maze apparatuses

Exploratory and anxiety-like behaviors were assessed in the open

field (OF) and elevated plus maze (EPM) tests. The OF apparatus was a square wooden chamber (45 × 45 × 30 cm) with white walls and floor. Mice were placed in the center and allowed to explore freely for 5 min. The EPM consisted of four white plexiglass arms (each 30 cm long, 5 cm wide) elevated 70 cm above the floor. Two opposing arms were open, while the other two were enclosed by 16 cm high opaque walls. Each mouse was placed in the central platform and allowed to explore for 5 min. Illumination was set to 10 lx. Behavior was recorded at 30 FPS using an overhead video camera (Logitech).

2.2.1. Data analysis

In the OF test, the total distance traveled and the time spent in the central zone (defined as 70 % of the arena area) were quantified. In the EPM, total distance traveled and time spent in the open arms, including the central platform (5 × 5 cm), were measured. Behavioral sessions were analyzed using EthoVision XT 17.5 (Noldus Information Technology, Wageningen, The Netherlands). One APP/PS1 mouse was excluded from EPM analysis due to recording failure.

2.3. Prepulse inhibition test

Prepulse inhibition (PPI) was assessed using a startle reflex system (Med Associates Inc.). The standard short protocol (6 min) provided by the manufacturer was employed, consisting of acoustic startle stimuli presented with or without prepulses. The startle stimulus was a 10 ms white noise burst at 100 dB. Prepulses were 10 ms pure tones (4, 12, or 20 kHz) at 70 dB, presented 100 ms before the startle stimulus. Each session began with a 60 s habituation period without stimulation, followed by 55 trials separated by randomized inter-trial intervals (3–8 s). In block 1, startle-alone trials (16) and startle + prepulse trials (8 per frequency) were presented in random order. In block 2, startle stimuli were delivered at varying intensities (70, 80, and 90 dB; 5 trials each) to assess startle amplitude as a function of intensity. PPI was expressed as the percentage reduction of the startle response in prepulse trials relative to startle-alone trials using the formula: $PPI (\%) = [1 - (\text{prepulse trial} / \text{startle-alone trial})] \times 100$.

2.4. ABR auditory thresholds

Auditory thresholds were determined using auditory brainstem responses (ABRs) in mice anesthetized with isoflurane. ABRs were recorded in a sound-attenuated room, with body temperature maintained at 37 °C using an electrically controlled heating pad. Stainless steel needle electrodes were positioned subcutaneously: one over the mastoid ipsilateral to the stimulated ear, one at the vertex (Cz, positive), and a ground electrode in the neck. Recordings were obtained with an eABR system (BioMed Jena GmbH) and Sennheiser Momentum M2 headphones calibrated to IEC 318–4 standards. Tone pips (2, 4, 8, and 16 kHz; 5–10 dB steps) were presented. Pure tone bursts were used for acoustic stimulation, defined by a 2–3–2 cycle envelope (two cycles rise, three cycles at full amplitude, and two cycles decay); therefore, the stimulus rise time varied with stimulation frequency. Stimuli were delivered via earphones coupled to an ear-canal tube. The acoustic system was calibrated using a Brüel & Kjær 4134 microphone. The repetition rate was 21.3 Hz, with a 10 ms data acquisition window. Both ears were stimulated separately. Signals were band-pass filtered (180 Hz–1.8 kHz), averaged 200–400 times, and analyzed with eAudio software.

2.5. Histology

Immediately after ABR recordings, mice were overdosed with isoflurane and transcardially perfused with heparinized saline (5 ml/L). Brains were removed and processed using the FD Rapid GolgiStain™ kit (FD NeuroTechnologies, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions, as described previously (Svobodová Burianová and Syka,

2020). Coronal sections (180 μm) were cut on a freezing microtome (Microm HM400R, Germany), mounted on gelatin-coated slides, air-dried, developed, dehydrated, cleared in xylene substitute, and coverslipped with Permount (Fisher Scientific).

2.6. Neuronal morphometry

Sections containing the IC, MGB, primary AC, and ventral hippocampal CA1 were identified according to Franklin and Paxinos (2007). IC sections were sampled from bregma -5.0 to -5.3 mm, MGB from -3.1 to -3.3 mm, AC from -2.8 to -3.1 mm, and CA1 from -3.4 to -3.6 mm. The IC was divided into the dorsal cortex (DIC), external cortex (EIC), and central nucleus (CIC), and the MGB into dorsal (MGB-D) and ventral (MGB-V) subdivisions.

Tracing was performed under bright-field microscopy (Leica DMRXA) using a video camera coupled to a high-resolution monitor (Wacom, 3840×2160 px) and NeuroLucida software (version 2021.1.3, MicroBrightField, USA). For each animal, 15 IC neurons (5 per subdivision), 10 MGB neurons (5 per subdivision), and 10 pyramidal neurons each from AC and CA1 were reconstructed in 3D. Pyramidal cells were identified by the presence of a basal dendritic tree and a distinct apical dendrite.

To minimize truncation artifacts, only neurons with somata located in the middle third of the section were analyzed. Inclusion criteria required well-impregnated neurons with at least tertiary branches, minimal overlap with neighboring stained cells, and absence of major staining artifacts. Tracing was performed manually by one experimenter blind to group identity.

From 3D reconstructions of Golgi-stained neurons, the following morphometric parameters were quantified: soma area, dendritic volume, dendritic length (apical and basal), number of primary dendrites, branch points (*nodes*), dendritic terminals (*ends*), and spine counts and density. Dendritic complexity was further evaluated using Sholl analysis. All procedures followed our previously published protocol (Svobodová Burianová and Syka, 2020).

2.7. Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were performed in GraphPad Prism 10 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA). For neuronal morphometry, five neurons were randomly sampled from each subdivision of the IC and MGB, and ten pyramidal neurons from the AC and CA1. Neuronal parameters were averaged per animal, and these animal means served as the unit of analysis.

Cell body area, number of varicosities, and dendritic parameters (total length, volume, dendrite number, branch points/nodes, and terminal ends) were analyzed with two-way mixed ANOVAs with Group (WT vs. APP/PS1; between-subjects) and Subdivision (IC: CIC, DIC, EIC; MGB: dorsal, ventral; within-subjects). Spine density was analyzed in the MGB, AC, and CA1 using the same statistical design. For AC and CA1, the same parameters were analyzed with Group (between-subjects) and Dendrite type (apical vs. basal; within-subjects). Significant effects or interactions were followed by Sidak post hoc tests (WT vs. APP/PS1 within each subdivision/type). The number of basal primary dendrites, which could not be included in the two-way design, was compared between groups using Welch's unequal-variance *t*-test.

Sholl analyses of dendritic intersections, dendritic length, and spine counts as a function of radius were evaluated using two-way mixed ANOVAs with Group (between-subjects) and Radius (within-subjects), followed by Sidak post hoc tests at each radius; significant ranges are reported.

ABR thresholds were analyzed using two-way mixed ANOVAs with Group (WT vs. APP/PS1; between-subjects) and Frequency (2, 4, 8, 16 kHz; within-subjects). ABR wave latencies (I–V) and interwave intervals (I–III, III–V, I–V) were analyzed using two-way mixed ANOVAs with Group (between-subjects) and Wave/Interval (within-subjects)

separately at 8 and 16 kHz and at 70 dB SPL and 10 dB above individual threshold. Sidak's multiple comparisons test was used for post hoc contrasts; significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

For PPI, open field, and elevated plus maze data were analyzed using unpaired *t*-tests or two-way ANOVAs as appropriate. Normality of residuals was verified with Shapiro–Wilk tests, and homogeneity of variance with Levene's test. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. Open field and elevated plus maze

Behavioral analysis using unpaired *t*-tests revealed no significant differences between APP/PS1 and WT groups in all measured parameters (Fig. 1). In the open field test, the total distance traveled was comparable between APP/PS1 (1595 ± 679.9 cm) and WT (1563 ± 332.9 cm) mice, with no significant difference observed ($t_{17} = 0.14$, $p = 0.894$). The time spent in the center zone also showed no significant difference between APP/PS1 (139.1 ± 67.68 s) and WT (150.5 ± 45.5 s) mice ($t_{17} = 0.44$, $p = 0.667$). Similarly, assessment in the elevated plus-maze showed comparable performance between groups, with APP/PS1 (1186 ± 432.3 cm) and WT (1129 ± 442.2 cm) mice showing no significant differences in total distance traveled ($t_{16} = 0.28$, $p = 0.786$) or time spent in the open arms and center (APP/PS1: 73.84 ± 42.72 s vs. WT: 65.98 ± 47.56 s; $t_{16} = 0.36$, $p = 0.721$).

3.2. Prepulse inhibition of the acoustic startle reflex

APP/PS1 mice showed a pronounced disruption of sensorimotor gating (Fig. 2). PPI was significantly reduced at all prepulse frequencies tested. For example, with a 4 kHz prepulse, APP/PS1 mice exhibited markedly lower PPI than WT controls ($t(12.8)=4.33$, $p = 0.0008$). Similar reductions were found at 12 kHz ($t(14.9)=4.38$, $p = 0.005$) and 20 kHz ($t(12.6)=3.63$, $p = 0.003$).

APP/PS1 mice also displayed exaggerated startle responses to pulse-alone stimuli. Startle amplitude increased more steeply with stimulus intensity than in WT mice, as confirmed by a significant group \times intensity interaction ($F(3,36)=4.97$, $p = 0.005$).

3.3. Auditory brainstem response thresholds

Auditory thresholds, assessed by ABR recordings (Fig. 3), did not differ between APP/PS1 and WT mice at any tested frequency (2–16 kHz). Two-way mixed ANOVA revealed no significant main effect of Group or Group \times Frequency interaction (all $p > 0.3$), confirming preserved peripheral auditory sensitivity in both genotypes.

Analysis of ABR wave latencies and interwave intervals (I–III, III–V, I–V) at 8 and 16 kHz (70 dB SPL and 10 dB above individual threshold) showed no significant main effects or interactions (all $p > 0.05$; Fig. 4; Supplementary Table S5). APP/PS1 mice displayed small, nonsignificant prolongations of late components (waves IV–V) and longer III–V and I–V intervals at 16 kHz/70 dB.

3.4. Neuronal morphology

Golgi–Cox staining and reconstruction revealed consistent morphological alterations across all analyzed brain structures, including the inferior colliculus, medial geniculate body, auditory cortex, and hippocampal CA1. APP/PS1 mice uniformly exhibited reduced dendritic complexity compared with WT, with differences detected in virtually all parameters assessed. Representative examples of reconstructed neurons are shown in Figs. 5–8. For clarity, we refer to primary dendrites, branch points, and terminals as dendrite number, dendritic nodes, and dendritic ends in the Results and figure legends.

Inferior colliculus (IC). APP/PS1 neurons exhibited simplified dendritic arbors across IC subdivisions (Fig. 9). Total dendritic length was

Fig. 1. Open field and elevated plus maze performance. (A, B) In the OF test, WT and APP/PS1 mice did not differ in total distance traveled (A) or time spent in the center zone (B). (C, D) In the EPM test, no significant differences were found between genotypes in the total distance (C) or time spent (D) in the open arms + center. Data are mean \pm SEM; unpaired *t*-tests.

markedly shorter ($F(1,16)=40.47$, $p < 0.0001$), and dendrite number was also reduced ($F(1,16)=10.89$, $p = 0.0045$). Number of nodes and terminal ends showed Group \times Subdivision interactions (nodes: $F(2,32)=4.98$, $p = 0.013$; ends: $F(2,32)=3.94$, $p = 0.030$), with post-hoc tests confirming significant WT>APP/PS1 differences in multiple subdivisions. Sholl analyses revealed extensive reductions in dendritic complexity: WT>APP/PS1 at 20–130 μm in CIC, 30–120 μm in DIC, and 20–150 μm in EIC (intersections and length, all adj. $p < 0.05$).

Medial geniculate body (MGB). Dendritic degeneration was evident across both dorsal (MGB-D) and ventral (MGB-V) subdivisions (Fig. 10). Total dendritic length was reduced by $\sim 68\%$ in APP/PS1 mice (WT 1197 μm vs. APP/PS1 385 μm ; $F(1,17)=146.3$, $p < 0.0001$), and spine density was halved (WT 0.331 vs. APP/PS1 0.158 μm^{-1} ; $F(1,17)=48.1$, $p < 0.0001$). Node numbers and terminal ends were also strongly reduced (nodes: $F(1,17)=100.3$, $p < 0.0001$; ends: $F(1,17)=157.3$, $p < 0.0001$). Dendrite number was significantly lower in both subdivisions (MGB-D $p < 0.0001$; MGB-V $p < 0.0001$, Sidak post-hocs). Sholl analyses confirmed uniform deficits: WT>APP/PS1 across 20–140 μm in MGB-D and 20–150 μm in MGB-V (intersections and length, all adj. $p < 0.05$).

Auditory cortex (AC). APP/PS1 pyramidal neurons displayed shortened dendritic trees in both apical and basal compartments (Fig. 11). Total dendritic length was significantly reduced ($F(1,17)=94.4$, $p < 0.0001$), with a Group \times Type interaction ($F(1,17)=7.95$, $p = 0.012$) reflecting greater loss in basal trees (WT basal 767 μm vs. APP/PS1 basal 332 μm). Dendrite nodes were fewer in APP/PS1 ($F(1,17)=57.3$, $p < 0.0001$), while terminal ends were strongly reduced ($F(1,17)=59.8$, $p <$

0.0001), with both apical and basal showing significant differences (Sidak $p < 0.0001$ each). Spine density was lower in APP/PS1 ($F(1,17)=22.8$, $p = 0.0002$), with an apical>basal effect ($F(1,17)=17.0$, $p = 0.0007$). The number of basal primary dendrites was also reduced (Welch's $t(9.7)=5.90$, $p = 0.0002$; WT 5.0 vs APP/PS1 3.3). Sholl analyses indicated reduced intersections at 30 and 70–150 μm (apical) and 20–130 μm plus 150 μm (basal), and shortened per-radius length at 30–50 and 70–140 μm (apical) and 20–150 μm (basal).

Hippocampal CA1. APP/PS1 pyramidal neurons showed profound dendritic degeneration in both apical and basal trees (Fig. 12). Total dendritic length was reduced by more than half (apical: WT 1086 vs. APP/PS1 466 μm , $p < 0.0001$; basal: WT 1141 vs. APP/PS1 340 μm , $p < 0.0001$). Dendrite nodes were fewer (apical: WT 9.47 vs. APP/PS1 3.53, $p < 0.0001$; basal: WT 7.90 vs. APP/PS1 2.77, $p < 0.0001$), and terminal ends were also reduced (apical: WT 10.69 vs. APP/PS1 4.57, $p < 0.0001$; basal: WT 12.96 vs. APP/PS1 5.96, $p < 0.0001$). Spine density was halved in both compartments (apical: WT 0.464 vs. APP/PS1 0.205 μm^{-1} , $p < 0.0001$; basal: WT 0.449 vs. APP/PS1 0.203 μm^{-1} , $p < 0.0001$). The number of basal primary dendrites was also significantly reduced ($t(13.35)=2.85$, $p = 0.0135$). Sholl analyses demonstrated broad deficits: WT>APP/PS1 at 20–150 μm for basal intersections, 30–150 μm for basal length, 40–150 μm for apical intersections, and 50–150 μm for apical length.

Analyses of cell body area, varicosities counts, dendritic parameters (including dendritic volume), and Sholl analysis of spine counts across all structures are presented in the Supplementary File.

Fig. 2. Prepulse inhibition (PPI) of the acoustic startle reflex. (A–C) PPI at prepulse frequencies of 4 kHz (A), 12 kHz (B), and 20 kHz (C). Startle pulse intensity was 100 dB, and prepulse intensity 70 dB. WT mice showed robust inhibition of the startle response, whereas APP/PS1 mice exhibited markedly reduced PPI at all frequencies. (D) Startle amplitude as a function of stimulus intensity (70–100 dB). APP/PS1 mice displayed significantly larger startle responses compared with WT. Data are mean ± SEM. ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ (unpaired t -test for PPI; two-way ANOVA with Sidak post hoc test for startle response).

Fig. 3. Auditory brainstem response (ABR) thresholds. Hearing thresholds were determined at 2, 4, 8, and 16 kHz in WT and APP/PS1 mice. No significant differences were observed between groups across the tested frequencies. Data are mean ± SEM; two-way ANOVA revealed no significant main effect of genotype or genotype × frequency interaction.

4. Discussion

Auditory function and related neural morphology were systematically assessed in 10-month-old APP/PS1 mice. ABR thresholds across

Fig. 4. Latencies of ABR waves I–V and interwave intervals in WT and APP/PS1 mice at 16 kHz stimulation (70 dB). Data are mean ± SD. Group differences were analyzed using two-way mixed ANOVAs followed by Sidak’s multiple comparisons test ($p < 0.05$). No statistically significant differences were detected between genotypes.

Fig. 5. Inferior colliculus (IC) neurons (Golgi-Cox staining and 3D tracings). (A) Atlas view of the inferior colliculus (IC) with its dorsal (DIC), central (CIC), and external (EIC) subdivisions, from which neurons were sampled. (B) Low-magnification image of Golgi-Cox-stained IC neurons. (C–E) Higher magnification images of representative neurons from WT mice in DIC (C), CIC (D), and EIC (E). (F–H) Corresponding images from APP/PS1 mice in DIC (F), CIC (G), and EIC (H). (I–K) Neurolucida tracings of IC neurons from WT mice in DIC (I), CIC (J), and EIC (K). (L–N) Tracings from APP/PS1 mice in DIC (L), CIC (M), and EIC (N). Stained and traced neurons are independent examples. Scale bars: 200 μm (B), 50 μm (C–N).

2–16 kHz were comparable to wild-type controls, and wave latencies and interpeak intervals showed only minor, nonsignificant prolongations of late components at 16 kHz. In contrast, prepulse inhibition of the acoustic startle reflex was profoundly reduced, and morphometric analyses revealed extensive dendritic degeneration within the inferior colliculus, medial geniculate body, auditory cortex, and ventral hippocampal CA1.

Our data showed only minimal differences in ABR wave latencies

and interpeak intervals, with a mild trend toward prolonged wave V latency and extended I–V and III–V intervals at 16 kHz at the supra-threshold level; however, these changes were not statistically significant. Previous reports have yielded variable results. Liu et al. (2020) found prolonged wave II latency and extended I–II and I–V intervals in 3-month-old APP/PS1 mice, whereas Na et al. (2023) observed delayed wave IV latency and an extended I–IV interval in 13-month-old animals—both consistent with our trend toward delayed central

Fig. 6. Medial geniculate body (MGB) neurons (Golgi-Cox staining and 3D tracings). (A) Atlas depiction of the medial geniculate body (MGB), showing the dorsal (MGB-D) and ventral (MGB-V) subdivisions targeted for analysis. (B) Low-magnification image of Golgi-Cox-stained neurons in the MGB. (C, E) Higher magnification of Golgi-Cox-stained neurons in MGB-V from a WT mouse (C) and an APP/PS1 mouse (E). (D, F) Higher magnification of neurons in MGB-D from a WT mouse (D) and an APP/PS1 mouse (F). (G–J) Neurolucida tracings of representative neurons: WT (G, H) and APP/PS1 (I, J), corresponding to MGB-V and MGB-D, respectively. Stained and traced neurons are independent examples. Scale bars: 200 μm (B), 50 μm (C–J).

components, suggesting reduced neural synchrony and possible demyelination within the central auditory pathway. Similar prolongations were reported by [Burke et al. \(2024\)](#) in the PS19/P301S model. In contrast, [Na et al. \(2023\)](#) described shorter wave I latencies and reduced I–IV intervals in 5xFAD mice, indicating enhanced central gain, while [O’Leary et al. \(2017\)](#) noted minimal latency changes in the same strain. Increased central gain (hyperexcitability) in 5xFAD mice is further supported by decreased wave I and increased wave IV amplitudes ([Na](#)

[et al., 2023](#)). In the APP/PS1 model, [Na et al. \(2023\)](#) reported reduced wave I amplitude without change in wave IV, whereas [Liu et al. \(2020\)](#) observed decreases in waves I, III, and V. Collectively, ABR findings point to peripheral hypoactivity in some AD mouse models and heterogeneous central responses—from slowed conduction to increased central gain—underscoring model- and age-dependent differences in auditory processing; in our APP/PS1 cohort, such central timing effects were subtle and not statistically significant..

Fig. 7. Auditory cortex (AC) pyramidal neurons (Golgi–Cox staining and 3D tracings). (A) Atlas representation of the auditory cortex (AC), highlighting the primary auditory area where pyramidal neurons were examined. (B) Low-magnification image of Golgi–Cox-stained AC neurons. (C, D) Higher magnification images of individual stained neurons from a WT mouse (C) and an APP/PS1 mouse (D). (E, F) NeuroLucida tracings of representative AC pyramidal neurons from a WT mouse (E) and an APP/PS1 mouse (F). The stained and traced neurons are independent examples. Scale bars: 200 μm (B), 50 μm (C, D), 100 μm (E, F).

In terms of ABR-measured hearing thresholds, these appeared to remain intact, contrasting with [Liu et al. \(2020\)](#), who reported elevated thresholds in APP/PS1 mice. By contrast, [Na et al. \(2023\)](#) found no significant ABR threshold differences, consistent with our results, and also reported unchanged DPOAEs—findings that seem more plausible, given the recorded ABR waveforms, than those of [Liu et al. \(2020\)](#).

Among the factors that may underlie discrepancies between studies, mouse age appears critical: 3 months in [Liu et al. \(2020\)](#), 10 months in our study, and 13 months in [Na et al. \(2023\)](#). Sex may also contribute, as only males were used here and by [Na et al. \(2023\)](#), whereas [Liu et al. \(2020\)](#) did not report animal sex. Differences in anesthesia represent

another variable—our recordings were obtained under isoflurane, [Liu et al. \(2020\)](#) used ketamine–xylazine, and [Na et al. \(2023\)](#) used ketamine–acepromazine and likewise observed no threshold differences. Isoflurane has been reported to elevate auditory thresholds compared with ketamine–xylazine in mice ([Verdoodt et al., 2021](#)) and rats ([Ruebhausen et al., 2012](#)), although other studies found no effect in either species ([Kim et al., 2012](#); [Bielefeld et al., 2014](#)). Because both APP/PS1 and WT mice in our study were tested under isoflurane, any anesthesia-related threshold shift should have affected both groups similarly. This interpretation aligns with [Na et al. \(2023\)](#), who also reported no genotype differences under ketamine–acepromazine.

Fig. 8. Hippocampal CA1 neurons (Golgi–Cox staining and 3D tracings). (A) Atlas schematic of the ventral hippocampal CA1 region; “Py” marks the pyramidal layer, the sampling site of pyramidal neurons. (B) Low-magnification image of Golgi–Cox-stained CA1 pyramidal neurons. (C, D) Higher magnification images of individual stained neurons from a WT mouse (C) and an APP/PS1 mouse (D). (E, F) NeuroLucida tracings of representative CA1 pyramidal neurons from a WT mouse (E) and an APP/PS1 mouse (F). The stained and traced neurons are independent examples. Scale bars: 200 μm (B), 50 μm (C, D), 100 μm (E, F).

Additional methodological differences include stimulus delivery, with earphones used here and by Na et al. (2023) but free-field loudspeakers by Liu et al. (2020). Collectively, these factors—particularly age, which strongly influences auditory function—likely account for the contrasting results, a conclusion further supported by Na et al. (2023).

While the primary auditory function of sound detection remained intact, as demonstrated by normal ABRs, a more complex function—prepulse inhibition (PPI) of the acoustic startle response—was severely impaired. We cannot exclude the possibility that pathology of the peripheral auditory system contributed to the changes observed in APP/PS1 mice, since our study did not focus on the basic circuitry of the

startle reflex and PPI. However, PPI is a complex process involving multiple brain regions including primary auditory cortex, ventral hippocampus, and basolateral amygdala (Rohleder et al., 2016). In our WT mice, PPI reduced the startle amplitude by approximately 50 %, consistent with previous reports (Wang et al., 2012; Cheng et al., 2014; O’Leary et al., 2018). In contrast, APP/PS1 mice showed almost no inhibition, independent of prepulse frequency. Previous studies reported smaller PPI in APP/PS1 compared with controls, but the difference was less pronounced than in our data, likely due to methodological differences. For example, those studies used a 120 dB startle pulse, whereas we used 100 dB, which may have increased the sensitivity of our

IC

Fig. 9. Morphometrical alterations of inferior colliculus (IC) neurons. Quantitative analysis of Golgi–Cox-stained neurons from the central (CIC), dorsal (DIC), and external (EIC) subdivisions. Compared with WT, APP/PS1 mice displayed shorter dendrites, reduced numbers of dendritic nodes and ends, and fewer primary dendrites, except for non-significant differences in dendrite number in DIC and dendritic nodes in CIC. Sholl analysis confirmed reduced dendritic intersections and length across radii in all subdivisions. Data are mean ± SEM. ns = not significant; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Gray shading indicates radii with significant group differences (two-way ANOVA with Sidak post hoc test, $p < 0.05$).

paradigm. O’Leary et al. (2018) also noted that the reduction of PPI in APP/PS1 mice might reach significance with larger sample sizes. In addition, we observed that the startle pulse elicited significantly larger responses in APP/PS1 mice than in WT, whereas earlier studies found only a non-significant trend. This finding resembles the enhanced central gain typically observed after noise exposure (e.g., Auerbach et al., 2019). We cannot exclude the possibility that pathological changes in the morphology of auditory neurons in APP/PS1 mice may produce functional alterations resembling enhanced central gain. Taken together, our findings suggest that the profound PPI deficit in APP/PS1 mice may be related to pathological changes in the auditory system, particularly in the IC, which is known to contribute to the modulation of the acoustic startle response (Leitner and Cohen, 1985; Lauer et al., 2017).

It should be noted that ABR thresholds were measured only at 2–16 kHz, whereas prepulse inhibition was tested at 4, 12, and 20 kHz. We selected these prepulse frequencies to probe both mid and high-

frequency ranges that are behaviorally relevant for mice and within the normal hearing range of the C57BL/6 background at this age. Although ABR data at 12 and 20 kHz were not collected, the absence of group differences up to 16 kHz suggests that peripheral sensitivity was comparable between genotypes across most of the frequency spectrum. The 4 kHz prepulse was presented at 70 dB SPL—close to the detection threshold—but this parameter was identical for both groups and thus cannot explain the large genotype differences in PPI. Therefore, the PPI deficit likely reflects central rather than peripheral auditory dysfunction.

APP/PS1 mice are not the only model of Alzheimer’s disease that exhibit progressive changes in auditory processing with age. Similar alterations have been reported in 5xFAD mice, another transgenic model of Alzheimer’s disease. These mice display robust gap detection deficits that emerge at about 2 months of age and worsen progressively (Kaylegian et al., 2019). A reduced acoustic startle response was also described in 5xFAD mice at 3 months of age (O’Leary et al., 2017). Thus,

MGB

Fig. 10. Dendritic degeneration in the medial geniculate body (MGB). Morphometric analysis of neurons in dorsal (MGB-D) and ventral (MGB-V) subdivisions revealed significant reductions in spine density, dendritic length, number, nodes, and dendrite ends in APP/PS1 mice compared with WT. Sholl analysis further demonstrated reduced dendritic complexity across radii in both subdivisions. Data are mean \pm SEM. **** $p < 0.0001$. Gray shading indicates radii with significant group differences (two-way ANOVA with Sidak post hoc test, $p < 0.05$).

AC

Fig. 11. Morphometric deficits in the auditory cortex (AC). APP/PS1 pyramidal neurons exhibited pronounced reductions in spine density, dendritic length, nodes, and ends in both apical and basal dendrites. The number of basal primary dendrites was also decreased. Sholl analysis confirmed significant reductions in dendritic intersections and length across radii, affecting both apical and basal compartments. Data are mean \pm SEM. ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$. Gray shading indicates radii with significant group differences (two-way ANOVA with Sidak post hoc test, $p < 0.05$).

CA1

Fig. 12. Structural pathology of hippocampal CA1 pyramidal neurons. APP/PS1 neurons displayed reduced spine density, dendritic length, nodes, and ends in both apical and basal compartments. The number of basal primary dendrites was also reduced. Sholl analysis revealed significant reductions in dendritic intersections and length across radii. Data are mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$, **** $p < 0.0001$. Gray shading indicates radii with significant group differences (two-way ANOVA with Sidak post hoc test, $p < 0.05$).

pathological involvement of the auditory system appears to be a consistent feature across Alzheimer’s disease mouse models, and morphological abnormalities may underlie the observed alterations in acoustic behavior. However, with the exception of dendritic spine loss, little was previously known about dendritic and network-level pathology in these transgenic lines. Our results demonstrate that dendritic changes in 10-month-old APP/PS1 mice are profound and widespread.

The morphometric analyses revealed a consistent pattern of dendritic degeneration in APP/PS1 mice across the central auditory system. In the IC, dendritic shortening was the most pronounced alteration, whereas reductions in dendrite number and dendritic nodes were less marked, particularly in the DIC and CIC, respectively. In contrast, the MGB and AC showed more uniform and severe degeneration, with highly significant reductions across all dendritic parameters, including spine density. Sholl analyses confirmed these findings, demonstrating reduced dendritic intersections and length in IC, MGB, and AC, consistent with a profound loss of dendritic complexity in the auditory system of APP/PS1 mice.

The morphological changes observed in the central auditory system of APP/PS1 mice were paralleled by similar alterations in the ventral hippocampal CA1 region. With the exception of a modest reduction in dendrite number, all other parameters—including spine density—showed pronounced decreases. The reduction in spines is consistent with previous reports in APP/PS1 mice. Moolman et al. (2004) described significant decreases in spine number and total dendritic area in the hippocampus at 11 months of age. Mérimo-Serrais et al. (2011) further reported layer-specific reductions in dendritic spine neck length and an increased frequency of spines with small head volume in CA1. Using in vivo imaging, Ren et al. (2025) observed progressive spine elimination, particularly on tertiary dendrites, in 14-month-old APP/PS1 mice.

In contrast to earlier reports that focused mainly on spine alterations in APP/PS1 mice, our study is the first to provide a detailed description

of dendritic changes in both the hippocampus and the central auditory system in this model. A similar morphometric approach, including Sholl analysis, was employed by Mehder et al. (2020) in a mouse model of late-onset Alzheimer’s disease based on deletion of aldehyde dehydrogenase 2. That model exhibited age-related accumulation of amyloid- β , phosphorylated tau, and other Alzheimer’s-like pathologies, accompanied by progressive deficits in recognition and spatial memory. Consistent with our findings in CA1, Mehder et al. (2020) reported significant reductions in apical and basal dendritic length, intersections, branch points, and ends, along with spine loss. However, unlike the pronounced dendritic degeneration we observed in the auditory cortex of APP/PS1 mice, their model showed no comparable changes in the primary somatosensory cortex.

The neuronal pathologies we observed may relate, at least in part, to the distribution of amyloid plaques in these regions. Na et al. (2023) reported that in 13-month-old APP/PS1 mice, amyloid plaques were present in the hippocampal CA1 and the auditory cortex, but absent from the MGB and IC. However, the relationship between plaques and dendritic pathology remains complex. Moolman et al. (2004) noted that although dystrophic dendrites often occur near amyloid deposits, most are found at sites distant from plaques. Similarly, Mérimo-Serrais et al. (2011) estimated that plaques occupy less than 2 % of the neuropil in APP/PS1 mice, suggesting that widespread dendritic degeneration cannot be explained solely by local plaque deposition.

In terms of behavioral outcomes, previous studies have yielded mixed results regarding exploratory and anxiety-like behavior in APP/PS1 mice assessed in the open field and elevated plus maze. Some reports described increased anxiety or reduced exploration, particularly in female mice (Cheng et al., 2014), whereas others found no genotype-related differences in male cohorts of comparable age (O’Leary et al., 2018). Likewise, Locci et al. (2021) and Webster et al. (2013) reported no alterations in open field or elevated plus maze

performance at 9–11 months, and Olesen et al. (2016) detected behavioral changes only after 12 months. Consistent with these latter findings, our 10-month-old male APP/PS1 mice showed normal locomotor and anxiety-related behavior in both tests. This supports the conclusion that the profound deficit in prepulse inhibition observed in our study is not secondary to generalized anxiety or hypoactivity.

In summary, our study demonstrates that APP/PS1 mice exhibit profound deficits in the PPI despite preserved peripheral hearing, accompanied by widespread dendritic degeneration in central auditory structures and ventral hippocampal CA1. These findings indicate that auditory dysfunction in this model is most consistent with central pathology, though peripheral contributions cannot be excluded. By providing the first detailed morphometric description of dendritic changes in the auditory pathway of APP/PS1 mice, our data suggest that structural degeneration along this system may critically contribute to impaired sensorimotor gating and represent a potential target for early detection and therapeutic intervention.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

The authors used Chat GPT 5 to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. The authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jana Svobodová Burianová: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Daniela Černotová:** Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Tereza Klausová:** Investigation. **Oliver Profant:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jakub Fuksa:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Josef Syka:** Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jan Svoboda:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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